

Quiet Quitting versus Empty Desk Mobbing: two sides of the same coin?

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The term *quiet quitting* describes a situation when an employee does the work that is expected of the position, but without going above and beyond what is expected¹.

It has been postulated that this phenomenon, understood as more prevalent because of COVID-19 pandemic, especially in health-care sector, might be associated with a period of work-related burnout and inability to maintain the work-life balance, while not being provided with proportional reward or opportunity for growth (this may be further understood as JoJo-effect: burnout causes the sudden loss of interest), resulting in disengagement. However, in the employer-employee relationship, there are always two sides of a story, which means that the quiet quitting might be directly related to empty desk mobbing, or to oscillation between full desk and empty desk mobbing, creating thus the corresponding oscillation in an employee, from burnout syndrome to quiet quitting. Targets of *empty desk (table) mobbing* (or empty desk syndrome) might experience serious physical and psychological² consequences due to, but not limited to the complete or partial absence of adequate work tasks for a long period of time. *Cinderella mobbing* is a type of mobbing in which the abused person is obliged to do completely meaningless work assignments or

assigning work tasks are absolutely below the professional level of the abused person³. In the case of *full desk (table) mobbing*, the victim is overwhelmed with work tasks, short-term appointments, forced to perform tasks that damage the health⁴.

To conclude, the relatively new term quiet quitting should be further investigated in the context of mobbing, especially empty desk mobbing, and therefore it should be further explained whether are these two phenomena actually two sides of the same coin.

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